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An Analytical Study Of Caturvidha Abhinaya In Belur Temple Of Hoysala Period

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Abstract

Body is the medium of expression in a dance and the thoughts of the dancer are displayed with the help of postures, costumes and expressions. The dancer uses his Angas, Upāngas and Pratyangas- āngika; Lyrics and music- Vacika; Costumes, lighting and stage- āhārya; Emotional abhinaya- Sātvika abhinaya.

In the absence of paintings, the temple sculptures are the only evidence of dance of the past. The Nāṭya śāstra by Bharatamuni, Abhinaya Darpaṇa by Nandikeśvara, Lāsya Ranjana by Simhabhupala and Sangeeta Ratnākara by Sārangadeva are authentic texts.

Geetham avadharaya, Nrityam avadharaya - Dance as an offering to God, in the Aṣṭhāvadhāna Pooja. Chennakeśava Temple, Belur is an example of Hoysala Architecture known for Madanikas or Apsaras. In the Navaranga, Queen Nāṭyarāni śantaladevi, used to offer Nritya seva. śantala devi was the epitome of perfect feminine beauty and was the model for portraying Madanikas. Every Madanika figure depicts a dance posture with minute details of costumes, makeup and ornaments. śukabhāśini: Vasantha Sundari - Keśabandha, Venuvadana, tribhangi- Keśa-Sringara. Nagaveena- Koravanji- the statue of the Mohini, the perfect dancing posture in perfect symmetry.

The Āngika, Āhārya and Sātvika abhinaya is amply presented in the sculptures, be it Madanika or Nāṭaraja. The postures- hastas and mudras- defined in the śāstra are not static positions, but are actions or in motion. a study in depth and its adaptation on stage will enrich the Classical dance format.

Keywords: Abhinaya, Chaturvidha Abhinaya, Belur Temple, Hoysala, Nritya

Introduction

Body is an instrument used by the dancer to express herself, using the body parts classified as Angas, Upangas and Pratyangas. It is referred to Āṅgika Abhinaya. The Lyrics and the Music aid the expression by the body and is called the Vāchika Abhinaya. Here the dancer may sing or may be assisted by the musical ensemble. The atmosphere is created by suitable kind of make up for each role- Sātwika, Rajasika and Tamasika- and role enhancing costumes, stagecraft and lighting and that is the āhārya. The aim of the dancer is to connect to the audience and make them a part of his worship of the divinity, through physical and philosophical manifestations. He is a bridge between the Aatma and Paramātma. Its Sātwika Abhinaya.

The Caturvida Abhinaya represents the presentation on the stage. Natyaśāstra by Bharat Muni, pronounces about the Abhinaya in the Dhyana śloka of Naṭaraja, the presiding deity of Dance:

Āṅgikam Bhuvanam Yasya Vāchikam Sarva Vāṅgmayam

Āhāryam Chandra-Tārādi Tam Vande Sātwikam Sivam

Important Scriptures:

Indian Classical Art is Scripture based and the Natya śāstra by Bharat Muni is the classic text defining various aspects of dance. It defines art and artists. The texts like the Abhinaya Darpaṇa by Nandikeśwar, a commentary on Natya śāstra, Lāsya Ranjana by Simhabhupala and Sangeeta Ratnakara by Sārang Deva provide further commentaries on the finer aspects of the performing art and music. It is one of the sixty-four types of knowledge a person tries to be expert in. Art is revered and the artist is respected in every stratum of the Indian cultural scene. Art had assumed great importance in the culture of India and was an

integral part of day-to-day life including temple rituals.

It is difficult for us to imagine the performances of the olden days, in the absence of any documentary proofs like pictures, caricatures or paintings and other tangible evidence. As such, the sculptures found on the temple walls, forts and other monuments are the available proof of dance and dancer and its past grandeur. A study of the same opens vistas about the state of dance, importance offered and its place in the society.

Art as an offering to Gods

The Music and Dance is offered as the seva or offering to the Deity in Aṣṭhavadhāna Pooja by pronouncing “Geetham Avadharaya, Nrityam Avadharaya”. Dance and Music is an integral part of the temple rituals and also all the celebrations and processions during festivities. We have several dancing deities and Naṭaraja is considered the Naṭyādhidevata, Saraswathi is Goddess of Learning, Pārvathi is preacher of Lāsya, Nartana Gaṇapati and the Shiva’s Gaṇa is a known ensemble of Dance and music, Veerbhadra is known for a ferocious dance, Viśṇu in his Mohini Avatar is a mesmerising dancer who can bewitch the demons and Shiva alike etc. The gods are Art Lovers and so also the devotees. The temples have exclusive space earmarked for Nritya Seva called Navaranga in front of the Garbhagrihas. The space used to be utilised by the dancers to offer their Nritya Seva on all special occasions.

The Royal Patronage

Dance was revered and patronised during the reign of various dynasties like Guptas in North India and Cholas, Pallavas in the South. The Chalukyas of Badami, Kadambas of Banavasi, Rashtrakutas of Manyakheta (now Malkhed), Vijayanagar of Hampi, Wadeyars of

Mysuru and prominently Hoysalas of Halebidu relentlessly and vehemently supported artists be they folk or classical. They considered the temples a must for the social well-being and art is an integral part of social harmony.

Hoysalas as Art Lovers

The Hoysalas ruled most part of Karnataka between 11th and 13th century. They have built huge and imposing temples all over the state which spread to present day Kerala, Tamil Nādu, Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka. They have built more than 1500 temples and about 300 temples still remain, some are well-maintained and a few are dilapidated and neglected. They had Halebidu in Hassan District as their capital and the entire Mandya, Hassan and Mysore region was a kind of workshop for the sculptors who finally built the marvellous Belur, Halebidu and Somanathapura temple.

Hoysalas have built marvellous temples in almost all parts of Hassan district. The most prominent among them are Hoysaleshwara and Shantaleshwara Temples of Halebidu and Chennakeshava Temple of Belur. Both the temples boast architectural marvels and have a huge number of carvings on the walls, Gopuram, Jagathi and also railings. The Halebidu temple has carvings of Ramayana, Mahabharata, Bhagavata and also commoners in their daily social life.

Belur Temple - Sculpture

Belur temple is known for the depiction of celestial Apsaras in its most intricate carvings. The carvings of Celestial nymphs better known as Madanikas or Apsaras attract the art lovers and the common men alike. The Apsara-Devangana, popularly known as Madanikas, are the damsels depicted in sculptural forms in Hoysalas Temples. The overall

depiction of the damsels accounts for the beauty of these images. Apsaras forms a part of the group of demigods in the chronicle of the divinities, and find a mention in many ancient Indian scriptures and iconographic texts. The duty of the Apsaras is to take orders from higher divine beings and act accordingly, they are also singers, dancers, and in general, entertainers as well as assistants to Gods.

Viṣṇuvardhana's Queen Shantala Devi was considered to be the epitome of perfect feminine beauty and the Madanikas sculptures were crafted by portraying the queen as a model. She was well-versed in music and Bharatanatyam dance. Every Madanikas figure depicts a Bharatanatyam posture with minute details of costumes, makeup and ornaments. The Queen has demonstrated freedom of expression in the conservative society of that period. Darpana Sundari stands out for its beauty and perfection.

Natyarani Shantala used to offer her Nritya Seva regularly at both Chennakeśava Temple and Shantaleśwara Temple and both have huge space meant for dance. The place is called Navaranga in front of the sanctum sanctorum and the dancer used to offer herself to the deity and used to experience the ecstasy of Bhakti.

Madanika and other important sculptures:

Statue of Sala, supposed to be the first King of Hoysalas, fighting the lion is at the entrance of Chennakeśava Temple. Sala, at the orders of the master Sudatta kills the lion and it becomes the foundation stone of the empire. The same is adopted as the symbol of Hoysala Kingdom and is used in almost all temples at prominent places.

Apsara-Devangana, popularly known as Madanika, are the damsels depicted in sculptural forms in Hoysala Temples. Apsaras forms a part of the group of demigods in the chronicle of the divinities, and find a mention in many ancient Indian scriptures and

iconographic texts. The duty of the Apsaras is to take orders from higher divine beings and act accordingly, they are also singers, dancers, and in general, entertainers as well as assistants to Gods.

Sculptural art in Karnataka has contributed greatly to the tradition of Madanika images. The culminating point of their class, imagery and style may be ascribed to the Hoysala sculptures, as seen at Belur. Vishnuvardhana's Queen Shantala Devi was considered to be the epitome of perfect feminine beauty and the Madanikas sculptures were crafted by portraying the queen as a model or Roopa Darshi. She was well-versed in music and Bharatanatyam dance. Every Madanikas figure depicts a Bharatanatyam posture with minute details of costumes, make-up and ornaments. The surroundings and the companions are also intricately carved to depict a complete picture.

Darpaṇa Sundari -beauty with a mirror: a close look at the anatomy, proportions and features of her body parts, it is undoubtedly a classic piece of art. These intrinsic works of art with its exceptional beauty and quality have been termed 'poetry in stone'. Some of these sculptures are incredibly realistic and it is hard to believe they were carved out of stone. With a close look at the anatomy, proportions and features of her body parts, it is undoubtedly a classic piece of art.

Śukabhaṣīni : the dancer is in conversation with her pet parrot. The bangle on her right hand can be moved up and down. She has some companions helping her with makeup. The intricate carving of ornaments is mesmerising.

The Arch dancer- the dancer under a canopy with two of her accompanists playing on musical instruments. The tree and the creepers have been so beautifully carved. The anklets are neatly carved and the designs are excellent and appear modern even now.

Sundari and Kapi- a monkey are pulling the edge of her saree of Madanikas, she is going to beat it with a twig of a tree. The playful posture of the monkey is depicted.

Keśabandha- she holds a mirror having a handle and is arranging the curls on her forehead.

Lāśya-Nritya- Madanika is practising her dance with her maids accompanying her on musical instruments.

Tribhangi-Nritya- a lady is dancing stylishly by bending her body into three portions, one from the waist downwards, other from the waist to the chest and another upwards. This is said to be the most difficult one, so far, no other dancer has been able to exhibit it. This is apparently one of the most difficult postures to achieve in Bharatanatyam.

Keśa-Shringara- she is dressing her hair after the bath. The attendants are holding flowers and toiletry. This Madanika has washed her hair and is squeezing the water out of it. This depiction is seen on a sculpture inside the temple too.

Pony-tailed lady- she has tied her hair into a fine knot.

Drum Dance- she has a beard and moustache like a man, and she is neither male nor female. It is a strange sculpture. She is dancing holding a drum in her left hand playing upon it with her right hand. The fingers are inserted in the ropes of the drum and the carving is marvellous.

Naga Vīṇa-Dance- the expert musician is playing on her violin, which is in the form of a snake.

RudraVīṇadhari- she is standing holding the instrument and her maids are arranging

for a concert. It is a unique instrument sculpture depicting the intricate carving of Rudra Vīṇa.

Veṇuvādana - she is playing on her flute, and her attendants listening. A beauty after a sumptuous meal- she is returning from her dinner and is about to retire for rest. She has a banana in her left hand. Her eyes are sleepy and the sculpture is very intricate.

Gypsy-Girl- Kuravanji- she holds in her left-hand palm leaves and holds the right hand in a speaking pose.

Bhasma-Mohini Dance- the figure illustrates the epic story of God Vishnu who took the form of Mohini to kill Bhasmāsura. Bhasmāsura is a demon who is blessed with a boon to reduce anyone to ashes by merely keeping his hand on his head. Mohini entices him to dance and finally makes him keep his hand on his own head and get reduced to ashes.

Huntress- A bird sitting on the canopy behind, she is aiming at the bird. Kite-Dancer- she is dancing imitating the play of flying a kite. She is standing as if she is pulling the string of the kite using both her hands.

Viśwa- Mohini -World-Bewitching Beauty- her hands and legs are carved very nicely. The canopy above her left shoulder is intricate.

Abhimani – A proud lady- she is fully dressed and has put on all sorts of ornaments on her body. She is looking at her beauty in pride through a mirror. Symbolising someone who has a lot of pride in her beauty and is also very conscious of the same. The sculpture at the left (at her feet) holds up a mirror but is looking away- kind of telling her woman that she doesn't need a mirror.

A beauty in perfect make-up: the lady has put on her best dress and ornaments and is ready to go for a dance. The ornaments are intricately carved. It looks that she is recently married and has all bridal makeup and her toe is being adorned by a toe-ring.

Shantaladevi- She is the queen of King Vishnuvardhana and is celestially beautiful. She is in a dancing pose. She is wearing a gem just above the middle of the forehead. Gandharva Dance- she wears on her forearm, a good number of bangles, which give an impression of moving to and fro.

The statue of Mohini, is the most perfect dancing posture. It has been constructed in perfect symmetry, so that if you let a drop of water fall from the tip of her right hand raised above the head, it would touch her nose, then touch the left breast, tip of the left hand and finally land on the toe of her left foot. The statue of the Mohini, the perfect dancing posture in perfect symmetry.

Some of the statues are exceptional with regard to their beauty. For example: one Madanika figure is shown with a fruit tree canopy, where a small fly is shown sitting on the fruit and nearby a lizard is preparing to pounce on the fly sitting on a jackfruit. In another, an eagle is shown attacking a sarabha, which in turn is attacking a lion, which in turn is pouncing on an elephant, which itself is seizing a snake, which in turn is shown in the act of swallowing a rat. a sight that includes a pondering sage.

The carvings on the pillars are of Shiva in various forms including Naṭaraja with and also without Parvati, two of Bhairava, two of Harihara, four of Surya, five of Durga and Mahiśasuramardini and one of Kama and Rati, one of Gaṇeśa, Brahma, Saraswati, Garuḍa and Chandra. Other major reliefs are of Arjuna shooting an arrow into the eye of the fish during Draupadi Swayamvara, Ravana lifting the Kailash, Daksha, Bali and śukrācharya.

Conclusion:

The Angika, Aaharya and Sātvika Abhinaya is amply presented in the sculptures, be it Madanika or Naṭaraja. They are the demonstration of various aspects explained in Naṭya śāstra and other related texts. The postures- Hastas and Mudras- as defined in the śāstra are not static positions, but are actions or in motion. The position as depicted in the statues are the final poses after the specific motion of parts of the body. The ornaments are fashionable and imaginative like a Vanity bag, high-heeled shoes are only a few examples. The devata Hastas are as per Shilpa śāstra and the Karaṇas demonstrate as prescribed in Naṭyaśāstra.

These temples provide us enough proof of the Dance and its grandeur during the rule of various rulers, these benevolent rulers patronised art and culture and thought that art is essential for the overall harmony and social well-being of the society. The art not only enhances the quality of life, but also helps achieve the Chaturvidha Puruśarthas-Dharma, Artha, Kama and Mokśa i.e. four goals of life. The Hoysala period is considered the Golden Period in the history of Art and Culture in Karnataka and a study into it enriches the vision and creativity of the art pursuer.

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